

Proto-forms of Ainu markers of past and future tenses and their Sino-Tibetan counterparts

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Abstract

The past simple tense in Ainu is expressed by the postposition of *a* (used with singular forms) / *rok* (used with plural forms) which is the verb “to sit”. Its Late Jōmon Ainu (LJA) form is **ʔa*. The Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) counterpart is **ʔa* “to be at/in (a certain place)”. In some Sino-Tibetan languages, for example, in Kinnauri and Bantawa past simple is expressed by the suffix *-a*. Future simple in Ainu is expressed by the postposition of *kus ne*. The form *kus ne* consists of the copula *ne* and the component *kus*. The component *kus* is connected with the Ainu word *kus* “to go through”. The corresponding PST form is **qʷă̄t* “to pass through” / “to traverse”. In Kinnauri future simple tense is expressed by suffix *-to*, which originated from Proto-Kinnauri **thal-* “to pass” / “to cross over”, which in its turn originated from PST **qʷă̄t* “to go through”.

Keywords: Ainu language; Sino-Tibetan languages; Ainu-Minoan stock; Sino-Caucasian family; comparative linguistics

1. Introduction

Earlier it was shown that the Ainu language is a relative of the Sino-Tibetan family. Ainu and Sino-Tibetan languages demonstrate notorious structural (Akulov 2016, Nonno 2025b, Nonno 2025c) and lexical similarities (Akulov, Nonno 2024, 2025a, 2025c, 2025b; 2026; Nonno 2025a). Ainu is not a distant relative, but is a member of the Sino-Tibetan family, and Ainu is a relic of the Proto-Sino-Tibetan language (Akulov, Nonno 2026: 3 – 4).

The current paper continues discovering concrete similarities between Ainu and the Sino-Tibetan languages; this paper is devoted to discovering of Sino-Tibetan counterparts of Ainu markers of past and future.

2. The Ainu marker of past simple tense its proto-form and its Sino-Tibetan counterparts

2.1. Ainu marker of past simple

In the Ainu language the past simple tense is expressed by the auxiliary *a* (singular) / *rok* (plural) placed after the main verb (Tamura 2000: 111).

The auxiliary verb agrees in number with the main verb.

For example:

ek a “he/she came”;

arki rok “they came”.

Tamura Suzuko suggests that the form *rok* also expresses politeness (Tamura 2000: 111), that is completely incorrect. In the form *rok* there is no politeness at all, it expresses only plural number. And Tamura’s attempt to see politeness in the form *rok* is nothing else, but an attempt to impose Japanese patterns on the Ainu language. In the form *rok* there is no politeness. Politeness is not a matter of importance in Ainu, and is not as widespread as in Japanese. In terms of politeness, Ainu is much closer to English or Russian than to Japanese.

Kindaichi Kyōsuke writes that *a / rok* expresses perfective aspect (Kindaichi 1993: 293). However, we suppose that it is more correct to consider *a / rok* as a marker of past simple, not a marker of perfective aspect since in Ainu there are another auxiliaries expressing perfect aspect: *oker*¹ functions like present perfect tense, and *nisa*² functions like past perfect tense.

Kindaichi points out that the auxiliary *a / rok* is actually the verb “to sit” (Kindaichi 1993: 293).

In all Ainu dialects the verb “to sit” is the same *a / rok*.

The plural form *rok* was derived from the singular form *a* by adding the circumfix: *r - - k*, that was made of components *ar* “very” and *ki* “to act”, “to do”, “to perform” (Nonno 2016: 40). It is possible to represent schematically the history of this form in the following way:

**ʔar ʔa ki* → **ar o ki* → *rok* (Nonno 2016: 40).

The form **ʔar ʔa ki* is the form that supposedly existed in Late Jōmon Ainu (LJA)³.

All the syllables of V and VC structure of modern Ainu were ʔV and ʔVC syllables in LJA (for more details see Nonno 2015: 64 – 65, Tamura 2000: 21). That’s why the LJA form of verb “to sit” is reconstructed as **ʔa*.

2.2. Proto-Sino-Tibetan counterpart of LJA **ʔa* “to sit”

The LJA verb **ʔa* “to sit” has clear Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) counterpart – the verb **ʔa* “to exist”, “to be at/in (a certain place)”.

2.3. Examples of expressing past tense with the use of *-a* suffix in Tibeto-Burman languages

In some modern Sino-Tibetan languages past simple is expressed by suffix *-a*.

2.3.1. Kinnauri

For example in the Kinnauri⁴ language past tense is expressed by suffixes *-a-* and *-e-* (Takahashi 2021: 342).

¹ The verb *oker* means “to finish”, the form *oker* is derived from the root *kes* “end” / “edge” (Kayano 2005: 224).

² The verb *nisa* is a compound of roots: *ni* “tree” (Kayano 2005: 341) and *sa* that express the meaning of going down, the root *sa* can be seen in verb *san / sap* meaning “to descend” / “to go down” (Batchelor 1905: 388).

³ Modern / historical Ainu dialects started to diverge in late Jōmon (about 1500 – 300 BCE) (see Nonno 2015: 64), and when we make reconstructions after modern Ainu dialects we receive forms of Late Jōmon Ainu – the language that was the immediate ancestor of all modern Ainu dialects

These suffixes evidently are variants of the same morpheme.

These suffixes are attached immediately to the stem, and are followed by personal markers, for instance: *bid* “to come” → *bid-a-k* “I came”, where *-k* is the marker of 1sgsb (Takahashi 2021: 343, 340). This differs from the scheme of expressing past that exists in Ainu where the marker of past is a particle placed after the verb word-form. However, given that the Ainu language separated from the Proto-Sino-Tibetan language very early (the time of separation of Proto-Ainu is related to the beginning of the Jōmon period), such a small discrepancy in positional realizations can be considered insignificant.

Fig. 1. Location of Himachal Pradesh in India (image source – Wikipedia 2026)

⁴ Kinnauri is a Tibeto-Burman language (or a dialect cluster) of the Tibeto-Kanauri branch, the language is spread in the Indian state of Himachal Pradesh (see Fig. 1).

2.3.2. Bantawa

In the Bantawa⁵ language past tense is expressed by suffixes *-a* and *-∅* (Doornenbal 2009: 160). For example:

t̄-rimt-a-ŋ

2sgag-insult-PAST-1sgpt

“you have insulted me” (Doornenbal 2009: 174).

From this example we can see that the marker of past tense in Bantawa is attached immediately to the verb stem and is followed by a marker of patient. This scenario is the same as in Kinnauri.

3. The Ainu marker of future simple tense its proto-form and its Sino-Tibetan counterparts

3.1. Ainu marker of future simple tense

Future simple tense in Ainu is expressed by the postposition of *kus ne* (*kusu ne*)⁶ (Simeon 1970: 181; Tamura 2000: 160)

The auxiliary *kus ne* is the same for singular and plural forms:

ek kus ne “he/she will come”,

arki kus ne “they will come”.

The form *kus ne* consists of the copula *ne*⁷ and the word *kus*.

The component *kus* is connected with the Ainu word *kus* “to pass” / “to go through” / “to pass through”⁸. Also *kus* means “other side”, for instance: *pet kus* “opposite bank of the river”, *kus-un-kotan* “village on the other side of the river” (Chiri 2000: 54).

We suppose that the marker of future tense *kus* initially was the verb “to go through”, since thinking of the ancient people was very concrete and figurative, so the idea of future could be initially expressed by the idea of going through.

As far as the form **kus* “to pass through” is represented in all Ainu dialects, so it is possible to reconstruct the form **kus* for LJA.

The LJA form **kus ne* literally means “the passage exists”.

3.2. The Proto-Sino-Tibetan counterpart of LJA **kus* “to go through”

The LJA form **kus* can be correlated with the PST form **q^wāt* “to pass through” / “to traverse”.

⁵ The Bantawa language (also referred to as An Yüŋ, Bantaba, Bantawa Dum, Bantawa Yong, Bantawa Yüŋ, Bontawa, Kirawa Yüŋ) is a Tibeto-Burman language of the Kiranti branch spoken in the eastern Himalayan hills of eastern Nepal by Kirati Bantawa ethnic groups.

⁶ In different descriptions, the phrase *kus ne* is written differently, sometimes as *kusune* (Simeon 1970: 181), sometimes as *kusu-ne* (Tamura 2000: 160). These writing methods emphasize that the phrase functions as a single particle.

⁷ About PST counterparts of Ainu copula *ne* see Akulov, Nonno 2024: 17.

⁸ Chiri 2000: 54, Kayano 2005: 214.

This reconstruction is supported by several cognates across major branches of the family: Old Chinese: 越 **wat* "to transgress" / "to pass over". Tibetan: *rgjud* "to pass through" / "to traverse". Kachin (Jinghpaw): *kot*, "to step or pass over". Proto-Kiranti: **khwat* "to go".

3.3. Examples of expressing the future tense by **kV[C]* or alike suffix in Tibeto-Burman languages

In the case of future tense Tibeto-Burman counterparts are not as evident as in the case of past tense.

In the Kinnauri language future simple tense is expressed by suffixes *-to* and *-o*. (Takahashi 2021: 342).

For example: *bid* "to come" → *bito* "to come" (Takahashi 2021: 342).

This suffix *-to* originated from Proto-Kinnauri **thal-* "to pass" / "to cross over."

And Proto-Kinnauri **thal-* originated from PST **q^wāt* "to go through", "to pass through".

The shift of PST **q-* or **k-* into **t-* in Kinnauri is quite regular. For instance, PST **ka-n* (or **qa-n*) "bitter" correlates with Kinnauri *tij*.

Forms similar to Proto-Kinnauri **thal* can also be seen in other Tibeto-Burman languages, for instance in Written Tibetan there is the form *thal* "to pass", "to pass by", "to go beyond". In Lahu⁹ there is form *šā* "to pass through".

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⁹ Lahu is a Tibeto-Burman language of the Lolo-Burmese branch, it is spread in Southwest China, in Thailand, Laos, Myanmar, and Vietnam.

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